

Lanthanide(III) Monochloroacetate Complexes with Neutral Oxygen Donor Ligand

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In pursuit of our endeavour to investigate the preference and stabilisation of coordination number and structural probability of lanthanide ions, we report here the complexes of lanthanide(III) ions with a mixed-ligand system containing chloroacetic acid and γ -picoline-*N*-oxide.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses are consistent with the formulation of the compounds. The molar conductance of the complexes in nitrobenzene medium ($\sim 10^{-3} M$) indicate that they are essentially non-electrolytes. The magnetic moments of the complexes at room temperature (Table 1) show little deviation from the Van Vleck¹ values indicating the non-participation of the 4*f*-electrons in bond formation in these complexes. The magnetic moments of these complexes are within the pre-

dicted range². The molecular weight measurement indicates that the compounds are monomeric.

Infrared spectra of the complexes (Table 1) indicate that the ν_{N-O} , δ_{N-O} and γ_{C-H} of *v*-pic-*N*-oxide are present at lower frequencies as compared to the pure ligand, which suggests the coordination of these ligands through oxygen atoms³. The $\nu_{C=O}$ and ν_{C-O} bands of pure haloacetate shift to higher and lower frequencies respectively, on complexation (Table 1). The $\nu_{C=O}$ band of the carboxylate group is known to be particularly sensitive to the mode of coordination.

Electronic spectra of the complexes in the visible region indicate red-shift of the bands. The magnitude of red-shift (nephelauxetic effect) is dependent on the change in electronic repulsion parameter. The nephelauxetic ratio (β), percentage covalency param-

TABLE I – ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND IR SPECTRA (cm⁻¹) DATA OF THE LANTHANIDE COMPLEXES

Compd. (Colour, M.p. °C)	Analyses %: Found/(Calcd.)					μ_{eff} B.M.	Mol. wt. Found/ (Calcd.)	Chloroacetic acid		γ -Pic. NO		
	Metal	N	C	H	Cl			$\nu(C=O)$	$\nu(C-O)$	$\nu(N-O)$	$\delta(N-O)$	$\gamma(C-H)$
[La(ClCH ₂ CO ₂) ₃ γ -PicNO] (White, 156)	25.64 (26.28)	2.53 2.65	26.89 27.24	2.28 2.46	19.88 20.15	Diamag.	520.00 (528.54)	1 630	1 380	1 210	830	770
[Ce(ClCH ₂ CO ₂) ₃ γ -PicNO] (White, 145)	25.83 (26.45)	2.49 2.64	26.78 27.18	2.26 2.45	19.72 20.10	2.45	510.00 (529.75)	1 625	1 375	1 210	840	760
[Pr(ClCH ₂ CO ₂) ₃ γ -PicNO] (Greenish white, 155)	26.40 (26.56)	2.48 2.64	26.72 27.14	2.25 2.45	19.69 20.07	2.51	525.00 (530.54)	1 630	1 370	1 205	835	770
[Nd(ClCH ₂ CO ₂) ₃ γ -PicNO] (Pinkish white, 165)	26.80 (27.02)	2.41 2.62	26.61 26.97	2.11 2.44	19.67 19.95	3.49	532.00 (533.87)	1 630	1 380	1 215	840	770
[Sm(ClCH ₂ CO ₂) ₃ γ -PicNO] (Cream, 170)	27.41 (27.85)	2.38 2.59	26.43 26.67	2.09 2.41	19.53 19.72	2.55	538.21 (540.03)	1 630	1 370	1 210	835	770
[Gd(ClCH ₂ CO ₂) ₃ γ -PicNO] (White, 160)	28.01 (28.75)	2.33 2.56	26.02 26.33	2.03 2.38	19.33 19.47	7.33	542.00 (546.88)	1 620	1 380	1 200	830	760

eter ($\delta\%$), bonding parameter ($b^{1/2}$) and the angular covalency (η) values respectively, are 0.9796–0.9816, 0.9999–2.0824, 0.0091–0.0102, 0.009206–0.010407. The β -values are less than one and the positive values of $\delta\%$ and $b^{1/2}$ indicate that the nature of bonding between the metal and ligands is covalent⁴. All the compounds are non-volatile and stable.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Ln(III) complexes : Chloroacetic acid was added to Ln(III) nitrate in 1 : 3 molar ratio in ethanolic medium and the mixture was refluxed for 1 h. Then an ethanolic solution of γ -picoline-*N*-oxide was added to it in excess with constant stirring for 1 h and left overnight. The resulting solids were washed with ethanol and kept under reduced pressure.

The metal contents were estimated as metal oxides and chlorine as silver chloride. Microanalyses were performed at the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. Magnetic moments of the complexes were

determined by Gouy method at room temperature. The conductance measurements were carried out in nitrobenzene medium ($\sim 10^{-3} M$) by a Systronics 303 conductivity meter. Electronic and infrared spectra were recorded on Elico CL-54 and Shimadzu 408 spectrophotometers respectively. The molecular weight measurements were carried out by Rast's method using biphenyl as solvent.

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